

Polish Language Resources and Tools: Towards Multilinguality

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Abstract

The speech gives an overview of Polish linguistic resources and tools (LRTs): corpora, lexica (including two wordnets), morphological analysers, taggers, grammars and parsers, etc. It focuses on recent work on multilingual LRTs, including parallel corpora, especially on work carried out at the Polish Academy of Sciences on grammar induction from such parallel corpora.